

The HuT

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2.3. List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial intelligence
ASRA	Accelerator for Systemic Risk Assessment
DEM	The HuT Demonstrator
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EU	European Union
I-DRRnF	International Disaster Risk Reduction Nexus Forum
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MHEWS	Multi-hazard early warning systems
NBS	Nature-based solutions
RiskKAN	Knowledge Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SFDRR	Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction
SRA	Systemic Risk Assessment
SRR	Systemic Risk Responses
The HuT	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
UN	United Nations
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
WHO	World Health Organization
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

3. Acknowledgements

The organisers of the third International Disaster Risk Reduction Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) would like to thank all individuals and institutions who contributed to the successful organisation and implementation of the event, which took place on 24 September 2025 in Hamburg, Germany.

We gratefully acknowledge Jana Sillmann for the opening remarks and overview of the forum's objectives and agenda. We sincerely thank the keynote speakers and presenters for their insightful contributions and for sharing their expertise on systemic risks and multi-hazard disaster risk reduction, including Sirkku Juhola, Markus Reichstein, Ajay Gambhir, Sarah Hendel-Blackford, Zinta Zommers, Sony Kapoor, Alex Ruane, Alexandre Pereira Santos, Nicholas Simpson, and Joyeeta Gupta. We also thank Daniela Jacob, Jenty Kirsch-Wood, and Steven Klein for their contributions to the panel discussion, which provided valuable perspectives on systemic risk governance, policy, and practice.

We also thank Michele Calvello and Guido Rianna for their coordination during the preparation of the forum and their contribution to the I-DRRnF organisation and agenda setting. Furthermore, we thank all The HuT project partners and the ten The HuT demonstrators for their poster presentations and active engagement, which offered important insights into the practical implementation of innovative disaster risk reduction solutions across diverse regional and hazard contexts. We further acknowledge all partners and the broader community of researchers and practitioners who participated in the Forum and contributed to the rich discussions and exchange of experiences.

4. Summary

This report provides the minutes of the third International Disaster Risk Reduction Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF), which is part of The HuT project, and took place on 24 September 2025 in Hamburg, Germany. The report includes an introduction and conceptual framing of this year's forum (Section 4), summaries of the keynote presentations given, the panel discussion (Section 5.1) and demonstrator posters presented (Section 5.3). It includes also a synthesis that highlights recurring themes and takeaways (Section 6).

The HuT project addresses the growing challenges posed by climate change-induced extreme events like forest fires, droughts, heatwaves, landslides, floods and storms in Europe, by testing innovative disaster risk reduction (DRR) solutions. The I-DRRnF brings together The HuT partners and stakeholders to discuss and exchange DRR strategies, challenges and experiences, to deliberate on governance and policy mechanisms supporting DRR, and to analyse transfer and upscale of good practices and DRR solutions. This third I-DRRnF was held as the International Systemic Risk Conference organised in partnership between the University of Hamburg, GERICS, RiskKAN network (Knowledge Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events) and included the The HuT Innovation Fair. It comprised ten keynote presentations, a panel discussion and ten poster presentations in which all The HuT demonstrators presented highlight activities from their work.

The keynote presentations spanned across different realms of systemic risk. From systems governance, digitalisation and artificial intelligence, improved assessment frameworks, response mechanisms, systemic risks connected to current developments around the UN science-policy landscape, systemic risks in specific sectors such as finance, food systems, or urbanisation, understanding future vulnerabilities and the relationship of global systemic risks and questions of justice.

The Innovation Fair provided a space for The HuT demonstrators to present their DRR activities, share innovations tested across diverse contexts and reflect on how systemic risk considerations are increasingly shaping their work. Their presentations showed a wide range of DRR innovations for different types of hazards and in a regional diversity, spanning from Iceland over the United Kingdom, Lithuania, Germany, Hungary, Switzerland and Spain to Italy. The piloted innovations comprise advanced multi-hazard monitoring systems, including IoT technologies, early warning solutions, community-centred preparedness measures and nature-based solutions. Together, they illustrate how digital technologies, innovative governance arrangements, and locally tailored adaptation strategies can be combined in different contexts to address risks ranging from coastal storms to floods, landslides, droughts and heatwaves.

Together, the keynote and demonstrator presentations addressed systemic risks from complementary conceptual, sectoral, and practical perspectives, highlighting the need for a systemic understanding of climate change impacts in multi-hazard disaster risk reduction. Across contributions, participants discussed adaptive and inclusive governance, the growing role of digital technologies, and the challenges of translating complex risk information into actionable knowledge. The presentations also pointed to the relevance of normative frameworks, finance and insurance mechanisms, and public engagement as key elements for addressing systemic risks in DRR. Overall, the conference highlighted the importance of integrating systemic risk thinking into DRR efforts both within The HuT demonstrators and policy, practice, and research across the broader DRR community.

5. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the third International Disaster Risk Reduction Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) entitled “DRR and systemic risk” which was held in Hamburg on 24 September 2025. The I-DRRnF in an exchange and upscaling instrument format within The HuT project that aims at fostering reciprocal learning across hazards, demonstration cases, domains of expertise and at improving the transferability of DRR solutions at EU scale and beyond. The I-DRRnF members include representatives from each demonstrator, The HuT partners and stakeholders. The third I-DRRnF, for the first time, included an Innovation Fair that targeted participants of the International Systemic Risk Conference and the public to support transfer and replication of DRR efforts to an audience beyond the consortium.

The two previous editions of the I-DRRnF took place in 2023 in Valencia, Spain, focussing on effective stakeholder engagement and the co-creation of DRR solutions (D5.3, Abderhalden et al. (2024), see also Abderhalden et al. (2025)), and 2024 in Gerzensee, Switzerland, focussing on multi-risk approaches, in particular multi-hazard early warning systems (MEHWS) and nature-based solutions (NbS), and their implementation barriers and enablers (D5.7, Huland et al. (2025) and Huland et al. (submitted)). Building on the strong interest and engaged discussions that emerged around multi-risk during the second I-DRRnF meeting, this year’s edition followed along this line while placing a complementary focus on the systemic nature of (multiple) risks. While multi-risk approaches examine how hazards interact, coincide or trigger cascading impacts (Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024), systemic-risk perspectives highlight how risk unfolds and propagates within interconnected social, ecological and technical systems (Li et al., 2021). Together, these two lenses offer distinct but equally important insights for understanding today’s complex risk landscape (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023).

In contrast to the two previous editions of the I-DRRnF, this year’s format was not designed as a stand-alone The HuT event but organised as a Systemic Risks Conference in conjunction with RiskKAN and included the The HuT Innovation Fair. The event was jointly organised by the conference team from the University of Hamburg and GERICS and The HuT partners, in particular from the University of Geneva. The forum was conducted during the conference and included keynote presentations, a panel discussion and the innovation fair in which all The HuT demonstrators presented posters showcasing DRR efforts in their case studies. In this format, the core aims of the third I-DRRnF were (1) bringing together experts from different disciplines working on DRR and systemic risks, (2) fostering exchange between researchers and practitioners, (3) showcasing the challenges in systemic risks related to climate extremes and DRR, (4) gaining a better understanding of tools and data, and (5) creating new opportunities for cross-sectoral/cross-disciplinary collaboration on the topic of systemic risks related to climate extremes and DRR.

Systemic risks have gained increasing attention in science and policy agendas (Mitra & Shaw, 2023). They emerge from the interplay of climate change and natural hazards within a network of interdependent social, technical, ecological and economic systems (Ciullo et al., 2025). Such interdependencies mean that disturbances can propagate rapidly and develop into multiple, mutually reinforcing crises across systems. It is in this context that The HuT project addresses the growing challenges posed by climate change-induced extreme events like forest fires, droughts, heatwaves, landslides, floods and storms in Europe. Systemic risks often manifest in cascading effects that spread within systems and sectors such as energy, agriculture, health, finance, and others (Li et al., 2021). As such, systemic risks need to be considered in the design and implementation of climate adaptation and, in particular, in the design of DRR strategies (Belle et al., 2024). As a result, many existing risk assessment approaches, including methods, data

and tools, are not fit to capture the dynamic and cross-sectoral character of systemic risks. The focus on systemic risk also has important implications for the The HuT project. It supports learning across demonstrators and strengthens the transferability of DRR solutions by fostering deeper reflection on interdependencies between hazards, vulnerabilities, and governance structures. In this way, the forum contributes to more integrated approaches to risk management. The discussions further highlighted areas for future methodological development, particularly regarding the integration of social and institutional dimensions into risk assessment tools.

The keynote presentations offer different angles on systemic risks, ranging from social dynamics and governance aspects to methodological advances, science–policy interfaces, and sector-specific insights such as finance, food systems and urban contexts. The panel discussion further deepened selected themes. The ten The HuT demonstrator sites implement different disaster risk reduction (DRR) measures for different types of hazards in a vast regional diversity across Europe. In all The HuT demonstrators, hazards, vulnerabilities, and exposure are interconnected across social, ecological, and infrastructural systems - making a systemic risk perspective relevant (and possibly imperative) for effective implementation of DRR innovations. More precisely, in Valencia, Spain (DEM 1) and Ogliastra, Italy (DEM 8), intensifying heatwaves and wildfires demonstrate how climatic extremes may be amplified by existing social and economic vulnerabilities. In regions such as Val d’Aran, Spain (DEM 2), the Tisza River Basin, Hungary (DEM 7), and Vilnius, Lithuania (DEM 4), floods or landslides reveal cascading effects: a single hazard event can trigger multiple impacts across critical infrastructure, communities, and governance systems. Mountainous and coastal areas, including the Lattari Mountains, Italy (DEM 3), East Fjords, Iceland (DEM 6), Dorset, United Kingdom (DEM 9) and Bern, Switzerland (DEM 10), highlight how interdependencies between soil, water, monitoring and disaster risk management capacities amplify risk. Across cases, systemic risk is addressed through integrated monitoring, multi-hazard early warning systems, risk communication, participatory decision-support tools, innovative financial mechanisms and nature-based solutions; showing that resilience requires interventions that cut across sectors and scales and respond to the interaction of hazards with social, ecological, and infrastructural networks.

6. International DRR nexus Forum: Minutes from the third meeting

This section summarises the main contributions to the third The HuT I-DRRnF workshop, held on 24 September 2025 in Hamburg, Germany, during the annual meeting of The HuT consortium. It includes the keynote presentations and panel discussion (Section 6.1) and the demonstrator posters showcased during the Innovation Fair (Section 5.2).

A total of 345 participants attended the workshop, with 121 joining in person and 224 online. They included presenters, The HuT project partners and guests. The participants' backgrounds spanned across different scientific disciplines (e.g. meteorology, forestry, political sciences, engineering, economics, environmental sciences). Before the workshop, all presenters and participants were informed that the data would be used for this deliverable.

Table 1: Agenda of the third I-DRRnF

Wednesday, September 24, 2025	
09:00 - 09:20	Welcome and opening Opening remarks and overview of the Forum's objectives and agenda - <i>Jana Sillmann</i>
09:20 – 09:50	Presentation 1: Social dynamics and governing systemic risk - <i>Sirkku Juhola (University of Helsinki, Future Earth)</i>
9:50-10:20	Presentation 2: Early warning of systemic risk - AI to the rescue? - <i>Markus Reichstein (MPI BGC Jena, Risk KAN)</i>
10:20 – 10:45	Coffee break
10:45 – 11:15	Presentation 3: A framework to assess systemic risks in a global polycrisis - <i>Ajay Gambhir (ASRA)</i>
11:15 - 11:45	Presentation 4: Systemic risk responses: Lessons learned and a way forward - <i>Sarah Hendel-Blackford (ASRA)</i>
11:45 – 12:15	Presentation 5: Global shake-up: systemic risks and the changing science-policy landscape in 2025 - <i>Zinta Zommers (UN OCHA, IPCC WGII)</i>
12:15 - 13:00	Innovation Fair Introduction by Jo-Ting Huang Lachmann Poster presentation from the 10 The HuT demonstrators. <i>DEM 1, Valencia, Spain</i> <i>DEM 2, Val d'Aran, Spain</i> <i>DEM 3, Lattari Mountains, Italy</i> <i>DEM 4, Vilnius, Lithuania</i> <i>DEM 5, Glückstadt, Germany</i> <i>DEM 6, East Fjords, Iceland</i> <i>DEM 7, Tisza River Basin, Hungary</i>

	<i>DEM 8, Ogliastra, Italy</i> <i>DEM 9, Dorset, United Kingdom</i> <i>DEM 10, Bern, Switzerland</i>
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break
14:00 – 14:30	Presentation 6: Systemic risk and the finance sector - <i>Sony Kapoor (University College London, European University Institute)</i>
14:30 - 15:00	Presentation 7: Understanding and Modelling Systemic Risk in Food Systems - <i>Alex Ruane (NASA)</i>
15:00 – 15:30	Presentation 8: Systemic risk and adaptation: Focusing on the interconnections between future vulnerability and exposure - <i>Alexandre Pereira Santos (LMU Munich)</i>
15:30 - 16:00	Coffee break
16:00 – 16:30	Presentation 9: Understanding and attributing proportionality in drivers of systemic risk across diverse formal and informal urban contexts - <i>Nicholas Simpson (Climate Risk Lab, South Africa)</i>
16:30 - 17:00	Presentation 10: Climate change and existential risk - <i>Joyeeta Gupta (University of Amsterdam, Earth Commission)</i>
17:15 - 18:30	Panel Discussion - <i>Daniela Jacob (GERICS), Jenty Kirsch-Wood (UNDRR), Steven Klein (King's College London)</i>
18:30 – 20:00	Reception

6.1. Keynote presentations and panel discussion

The conference opened with a welcome address by Jana Sillmann (University of Hamburg) in which she emphasised the interconnected nature of global challenges, which can amplify each other positively and negatively, and the urgent need to consider systemic risks more widely. Mentioning examples such as the 2008 financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and climate-related disasters, she illustrated how shocks in one part of a system can cascade across sectors and scales, sometimes leading to systemic failures. With regards to The HuT project, she noted the relevance of considering multi-hazard risks, cross-sectoral, and systemic approaches to risk governance. Sillmann outlined five defining characteristics of systemic risk, namely (1) *scale* – ranging from local to global; (2) *relationships* – involving connections and cascading effects; (3) *system understanding* – encompassing uncertainties and data gaps; (4) *transboundary impacts* – with ripple effects across domains; and (5) *outcomes* – which are often negative, such as failure or collapse, though also offering potential for transformation. She noted that while systemic risks are recognized across fields from complexity science to governance, they are often understood differently. Advancing shared understanding requires progress in education, modelling, research, and governance, to which this conference and the I-DRRnF could contribute.

Key references: *Sillmann et al. (2022)*

6.1.1. Social dynamics and governing systemic risk - Sirkku Juhola (University of Helsinki, Future Earth)

Sirkku Juhola discussed how social dynamics and governance shape and potentially amplify systemic risk. She emphasised that while risks themselves are not new, their nature has changed due to increasing complexity, uncertainty, and ambiguity, as well as the profound societal shifts caused by digital transformation.

Drawing on governance theory, she explored how vulnerabilities emerge not only from hazards but also from governance systems themselves. She outlined different layers of understanding governance: as the internal workings of government, i.e. the bureaucratic structures and administrative processes, and as steering modes, i.e. broader institutions, norms, and actor strategies shaping social behaviours. Across these dimensions, digitalisation plays a transformative role; for instance, through automated enforcement systems, integrated data infrastructures, and algorithmic steering tools that influence public policy and individual behaviours. Juhola emphasised the role of emerging governance modes such as algorithmic regulation and highlighted examples ranging from open-data initiatives to China's social credit system as illustrations of how digital tools can reshape norms. The system provides an assessment of the social trustworthiness of individuals and companies. Further, she argued that understanding and advancing governance systems is crucial for reducing systemic risk. For example, a key requirement is transparency in algorithms and artificial intelligence (AI) applications used in public services. Juhola also pointed to social media-driven information bubbles as another mechanism through which actor strategies evolve in the digital age. As societies diverge on problem framings and acceptable solutions, governing systemic risk becomes increasingly challenging, making clear governance principles and accountability mechanisms more important than ever.

After the talk, the audience asked about implications for governance in multi-hazard contexts. An emphasis was placed on maintaining actor engagement and ensuring algorithmic systems do not unintentionally amplify vulnerabilities.

Key references: *Katzenbach & Bächle (2019)*, *Schweizer & Juhola (2024)*, *Veale & Brass (2019)*

6.1.2. Early warning of systemic risk – AI to the rescue? - Markus Reichstein (MPI BGC Jena, Risk KAN)

In his talk, Markus Reichstein discussed the intersection of early warning, systemic risk, and artificial intelligence, emphasising the need for a systemic perspective linking climate, ecosystems, and socio-economic systems.

Using the example of contrasting flood events in Germany, he showed that comparable weather events can have very different impacts depending on local terrain and conditions, illustrating how chronic risks interact with acute risks to amplify vulnerabilities. He elaborated the systems view on cascading impacts also for heatwaves, where the outcomes are determined by the interconnections of weather and climate systems, ecosystems, socio-economic systems, air chemistry and health systems. A key message concerned the importance of anticipatory action that saves lives, money, and time and contributes to enhancing resilience, demonstrating that early warnings pay off.

Reichstein presented AI as a transformative tool across the early warning chain that can facilitate linking hazard prediction, impact modelling, and communication. He argued that machine-learning models can deliver faster weather forecasts and integrate remote sensing, street imagery, and census data to anticipate impacts. He proposed the development of cross-domain models to

support integrated early warning systems. The integration of AI across sectors offers new opportunities, especially for the prediction of medium- and long-term risks. At the same time, he cautioned that AI itself constitutes a systemic risk that requires adequate governance.

In the ensuing discussion, questions focused on the utility of such approaches for prevention and links to engineering applications. Reichstein noted that the biggest potential lies in addressing *decadal-scale risks*, which remain insufficiently considered compared to short-term responses.

Key references: *Golding (2022)*, *Reichstein et al. (2021)*, *Reichstein et al. (2025)*

6.1.3. A Framework to Assess Systemic Risks in a Global Polycrisis - Ajay Gambhir (ASRA)

Ajay Gambhir presented the Systemic Risk Assessment (SRA) Framework developed by the Accelerator for Systemic Risk Assessment (ASRA), a UN Foundation initiative launched in 2023 to accelerate transformative action on escalating systemic risks.

He outlined the fragmented nature of the systemic risk field and explained ASRA's mission to galvanise a transdisciplinary network, catalyse science-policy integration, strengthen response capacities, and advocate for systemic risk strategies. The SRA framework helps to understand how risks interact, escalate into harms, and spread within and between systems. To guide the assessment of the global polycrisis, ASRA's SRA Framework draws on established principles across the PESTLE domains (politics, economics, society, technology, law, environment) and cross-cutting considerations, such as the UN Global Compact. The principles include, among others, universal responsibility, justice, individual and collective agency, multiple ways of knowing, uncertainty, complexity, transformation, all contributing to the overarching objective of mainstreaming capacity to address systemic risk. Moreover, Gambhir described the seven assessment steps of the SRA framework, ranging from understanding of the systems architecture, over mapping of interconnections, identification of possible responses, assessment of trade-offs and vulnerabilities, future storylines, dynamics modelling to implementation and monitoring, and corresponding cross-cutting practices that guide the assessments. The framework has been piloted across diverse contexts, from urban favelas in São Paulo to biodiversity in Indonesia, revealing challenges in systems mapping, the need for international standards, and the importance of including non-human species and their rights in assessments. The presentation underscored that effective systemic risk assessment requires integration across domains, careful consideration of institutional realities, and attention to implementation challenges in complex political and social contexts.

Discussions centred on how systemic risks can be considered in practice when facing constraining political realities. Participants noted that governance often operates under competing interests rather than a rational logic, creating barriers to implementing systemic approaches.

Key references: *(Gambhir et al., 2025)*

6.1.4. Systemic risk responses: Lessons learned and a way forward - Sarah Hendel-Blackford (ASRA)

Sarah Hendel-Blackford, also from ASRA, continued with a presentation on systemic risk responses (SRR) and criteria.

Defining SRR as any action that mitigates, prepares for, adapts to, or transforms away from the harms of systemic risks, she discussed how SRR can be assessed and improved and what gaps exist between existing frameworks and implementation in practice. She introduced a set of SRR

criteria that are based on ASRA principles but translate them into concrete criteria for assessing responses. These criteria help reveal both intended and unintended impacts, as well as the trade-offs. Her team analysed >40 examples of which they identified 19 systemic risk responses drawn from different sectors and governance levels, assessing each against 14 SRR criteria. The findings show substantial variation in how principles are applied: international initiatives tend to address complexity-related criteria on addressing inter-and intra-systemic risks but rarely address trade-offs; national responses often prioritise mainstreaming across departments but appear to pay limited attention to the intrinsic value of nature; and sub-national efforts commonly emphasise justice and compassion but engage less with uncertainty. She also underscored the anthropocentric bias in many assessment methods, pointing to emerging approaches that ASRA is investigating to incorporate non-human perspectives. The speaker closed with emerging lessons about why effective responses remain fragile: beyond governance and funding, they require attention to informal and formal power structures, committed champions across political lines, and a shift from reflection to reflexivity to surface biases and uncomfortable knowledge. She noted the importance of transformative responses that recognize and address causation, articulate a vision, and allow space for innovation.

Questions focused on potential misuse of systemic awareness and how principle-based approaches can help guard against dual-use risks without prescribing a one-size-fits-all solution.

6.1.5. Global Shake-up: Systemic risks and the changing science–policy landscape in 2025 - Zinta Zommers (UN OCHA)

Zinta Zommers is the Climate Science lead of the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UN OCHA) and Vice-Chair of the IPCC Working Group II. Her presentation focused on the recent geopolitical and financial shifts, how they are reshaping the science–policy landscape and what implications they have on systemic risk governance.

She described cascading impacts running across humanitarian, health, climate, and economic systems, shrinking the space for coordinated global science-policy action. She also pointed to the sharp decline in funding for multilateral institutions, which returned the UN system to resource levels last seen a decade ago. This “global shake-up,” she argued, creates systemic risks of its own: if institutions like WHO, ITU, or WMO lose capacity, core global functions such as pandemic preparedness, disaster response coordination, and climate monitoring could fragment or fail altogether. This shift requires us to rethink some of the existing tools and institutions and revisit established solutions. Zommers highlighted how these governance constraints directly affect climate policy. Without stable financing, international bodies like the IPCC may struggle to operate, undermining both the assessment cycles and the ability of states to agree on mitigation and adaptation commitments. She reflected on IPCC’s role as a boundary organisation that is meant to be policy-relevant but not prescriptive. Yet its structure, regional representation rules, and approval processes inevitably shape what becomes “agreed science,” raising questions about neutrality in a more politically charged era. Looking ahead to AR7, she noted efforts to ensure that the assessment remains relevant amid institutional uncertainty, including renewed attention to systemic risks and to tools and approaches capable of addressing them.

Ensuing discussions centred on whether the IPCC, in its current form, is fit for purpose in a rapidly shifting science–policy landscape. Moreover, questions focused on how global climate governance can remain functional when financing gaps pose systemic risks of their own.

6.1.6. Systemic Risk and the Finance Sector - Sony Kapoor (UCL / EUI)

Sony Kapoor discussed systemic risks to the finance sector, arguing that this sector is structurally more vulnerable to systemic risks than other parts of the economy and further explaining the causes and consequences of its vulnerability.

Regarding the causes, Kapoor explained that this vulnerability stems from the nature of financial products, which are often long-lived, highly abstract, and cannot be “road-tested” under real-world conditions. Their performance and resilience only become apparent once a shock (such as climate-related losses) occurs allowing failures to propagate rapidly across institutions. He further described self-reinforcing trends in finance, where rising prices can increase demand, which creates conditions for abrupt reversals. He also pointed to structural uniformity as a major driver of systemic fragility. Investors tend to use similar models and make similar allocation decisions, reducing diversification despite climate risks, fossil-fuel exposure, and housing market volatility. Likewise, global capital flows are characterised by a large concentration of investments in US assets. Diversifying and redirecting even a small share of capital, he argued, could have meaningful effects in other regions, e.g. for European competitiveness and development opportunities in the global south.

During the discussion, which focused on the impacts of increasing population and consumption, Kapoor noted several levers that could support a more resilient economic trajectory, including behavioural shifts, technological and material innovation, and policy frameworks that encourage low-carbon and resource-efficient choices. He also pointed to the growing role of remote work in globalising services, which may create new opportunities for more regionally balanced economic activity.

6.1.7. Understanding and Modelling Systemic Risk in Food Systems - Alex Ruane (NASA)

Alex Ruane explored how shocks propagate through global food systems and how modelling can support early warning, foresight, and resilience planning. He emphasised that different components of the system affect people and markets in different ways, and that isolating individual elements often misses the cascading impacts on other parts of the system. While many aspects of food systems can be modelled, the system as a whole remains only partially captured, pointing to persistent methodological gaps in representing cross-scale interactions and feedback processes, as well as in integrating machine-learning approaches.

Ruane explained that extremes in food systems are not solely caused by high-intensity events, but that slow changes in frequency, duration, seasonal timing, and spatial extent also play a critical role. He argued that specific climate impacts are determined by a combination of climate phenomena, vulnerability and exposure, which drive local responses. Therefore, modelling future adaptation requires consideration of responses such as future diets, farming systems, and alternative crops. He further pointed to the importance of identifying enabling conditions that reduce systemic risk and extend crop tolerance limits, such as foresight exercises and early-warning systems. He discussed the potential for buffering mechanisms to stabilise markets but also noted that these mechanisms can still leave systems vulnerable to cascading impacts and tipping points. Ruane concluded by stressing the importance of engaging stakeholders operating on different decision and climate shock scales.

In the ensuing discussion, the consequences of and applicability of models to tipping points such as a collapse of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation were discussed.

Key references: *Leal et al. (2023)*, *Nóia-Júnior et al. (2025)*, *Ruane et al. (2024)*

6.1.8. Systemic Risk and Adaptation: Focusing on the Interconnections between Future Vulnerability and Exposure - Alexandre Pereira Santos (LMU Munich)

Alexandre Pereira Santos discussed systemic risk and adaptation as complex challenges shaped by the interplay of social vulnerability and physical risk exposure.

He argued that conventional risk research often focuses on average population risks, a focus that typically attenuates or obscures the disproportionate impacts faced by the most vulnerable parts of the population. Potentially ensuing maladaptation is a risk because it can contribute to shifting vulnerability, misidentifying root causes, or allocating responsibility to the wrong actors. Systemic aspects of risk also emerge from deeply ingrained social processes that may set the conditions for self-reinforcing vulnerability.

Using case studies from Brazil, including COVID-19 impacts in São Paulo, he showed that highly vulnerable populations experience disproportionately higher fatalities, while less vulnerable population groups might even improve their quality of life instead. This contrast illustrates how risks can unequally impact social systems. He noted that gentrification, unequal development, and land-use changes further shape exposure and adaptation capacity. Santos discussed the trade-offs between breadth (diversity and coverage) and depth (integration) of research on systemic risks, which often leave critical gaps. He presented a framework for systemic-risk adaptation to address the need for integrated, multi-hazard vulnerability assessments: (1) transdisciplinary co-design of interventions and mixed methods design, (2) spatio-temporal risk assessment to establish the larger societal context, (3) exploration of social behaviour and divergent experiences in communities to identify evidence gaps and blind spots, and (4) a translator model for integrating different types of evidence. He emphasised that systemic adaptation strategies must integrate multiple stressors, acknowledge unequal capacities, and combine quantitative modelling with context-sensitive, socially-just approaches that capture feedbacks and contingent events.

During the Q&A session, he underlined the importance of complementing formal models with bottom-up assessments to capture qualitative aspects of vulnerability and adaptive capacity.

Key references: *Santos et al. (2024a, 2024b)*, *Peng et al. (2023)*

6.1.9. Understanding and Attributing Proportionality in Drivers of Systemic Risk across Diverse Urban Contexts - Nicholas Simpson (Climate Risk Lab, South Africa)

Nicholas Simpson discussed systemic risks in urban contexts, using Cape Town as an example and emphasising that impacts emerge from interactions between climate hazards, infrastructure, governance, and human responses. He stressed that traditional risk assessments often fail to capture these complexities because they focus narrowly on hazards, rather than the cascade of effects through social and technical systems.

Using Cape Town's Day Zero drought as an example, he illustrated how a combination of drought, water storage and treatment limits, tariffs, and household behaviours led to informal settlements and low-income communities being the most affected. He discussed interventions such as nature-based solutions like clearing invasive trees to improve river flows and emphasised the value of detailed household and street-level data for better risk planning. Simpson framed attribution as a central element in adaptation and governance cycles and introduced the Proportional Attribution of Systemic Risk framework, which measures the relative contribution of hazards, exposure, vulnerabilities, and responses to overall risk and can make complexity more actionable and governance more adaptable. The framework builds on risk budgets, inclusive attribution methods,

bridging quantitative and participatory tools and iterative adaptation to allow a focus on the most vulnerable while managing system-wide risks.

In the ensuing discussion, the audience asked how attribution can be applied in contexts with limited formal governance. Simpson pointed to the challenges faced in informal urban areas and highlighted the need for detailed local data, participatory approaches, and flexible frameworks that can adapt to complex and politically sensitive environments. He also reflected on the transferability of adaptation strategies, such as NbS and risk budgeting, across different urban and governance contexts, and the importance of learning from both successes and failures.

Key references: *Holden et al. (2022)*, *Simpson et al. (2021, 2023)*

6.1.10. Climate Change and Existential Risk - Joyeeta Gupta (University of Amsterdam, Earth Commission)

Joyeeta Gupta discussed the growing importance of systemic and existential risks arising from environmental degradation, including air and water pollution, biodiversity loss, and climate change, noting how much human health depends on a healthy planet. From a human rights perspective, existential risk is not just about the risks for humanity, but risks for humans, communities and countries.

She highlighted the unequal distribution of causes and impacts, where wealthier actors often drive environmental harm while vulnerable populations bear the greatest consequences. Gupta emphasized the need to move from conceptualizing justice to operationalizing it within climate and environmental governance through addressing the drivers, allocating liability, allocating resources and allocating responsibility. She presented a justice framework drawing on the Earth Commission, including recognition and epistemic justice, interspecies, intergenerational and intrageneration justice which contribute to transformational justice and feeds into procedural substantive (distributive, corrective and restorative) justice. Gupta stressed that environmental limits must be assessed not only for planetary safety but also to prevent significant harm to humans and other species, noting that (a) significant (and irreversible/ existential) harm to humans may be caused long before safe boundaries are crossed; and (b) many safe boundaries are already crossed. Addressing systemic risks requires considering inequities, power, and responsibility. She highlighted trade-offs, for example how rapid emission reductions may create new systemic injustices if vulnerable groups are disproportionately affected, and stressed the role of technology, governance, and policy in enlarging or constraining ecospace.

During the Q&A, Gupta addressed the challenge of operationalising justice across cultures and sectors. She discussed the role of businesses and the need for internalising environmental costs alongside other regulatory and economic instruments. She argued that effective systemic risk governance requires prioritising the protection of vulnerable populations and ensuring that those with the greatest power shoulder the largest share of responsibility. The discussion also touched on the challenge to translate justice considerations into quantitative metrics in risk assessment and modelling.

Key references: *Gupta et al. (2025)*, *Rammelt et al. (2023)*, *Rockström et al. (2023)*

6.1.11. Panel discussion

Panelists: Daniela Jacob (GERICS), Jenty Kirsch-Wood (UNDRR), Steven Klein (King's College London)

The panel discussion addressed systemic climate risks from the perspectives of climate services, disaster risk reduction, and political philosophy, focusing on how climate information, governance systems, and societal responses interact under conditions of increasing risk. Key topics included the role of climate services in preparedness and decision making, the convergence and remaining gaps between climate and DRR communities, challenges of scaling adaptation and risk reduction solutions, the political and financial dimensions of systemic risk, and the persistent knowledge–action gap. Cross-cutting issues such as insurability, risk sharing, data availability, justice, democratic decision-making, and the measurement of adaptation success featured throughout the discussion.

Daniela Jacob focused on how climate information can be operationalised to support preparedness and precautionary action, drawing on her work on climate services. She argued for the importance of disentangling climate drivers and system-specific vulnerabilities to design targeted adaptation measures. Jacob framed climate-resilient development as a unifying framework that combines adaptation and mitigation and stressed that climate services should support decisions taken before extreme events occur. She also pointed to the need for open and accessible climate data that is co-designed with users and embedded in local and sectoral contexts, while noting the challenges of defining and assessing standardised indicators for adaptation success due to their strong context dependency.

Jenty Kirsch-Wood addressed implementation, scaling, and risk financing from a disaster risk reduction and policy perspective. She drew attention to the growing challenge of uninsurability, noting that insurance systems are already under pressure in several regions, and argued for the proactive development of risk-sharing architectures at national and global levels. Kirsch-Wood stressed the importance of communicating climate risks in decision-relevant terms, such as expected losses and financial exposure, rather than focusing on uncertainty. She also outlined the need to link climate information to concrete products and services, including insurance mechanisms, urban planning, and investment decisions, and pointed to the economic case for adaptation through avoided losses and maintained insurability.

Steven Klein approached systemic risk from a political and philosophical perspective, focusing on governance under conditions of urgency and interconnected risk. He discussed how large-scale systemic risks challenge democratic institutions due to mismatches between political time horizons and the long-term nature of climate risks. Klein highlighted the paradox that institutions designed to reduce individual risks, such as insurance or welfare mechanisms, can inadvertently amplify systemic vulnerability. He also engaged with the normative dimensions of systemic risk governance, questioning the dominance of cost–benefit analysis and fixed notions of justice, and suggesting that inclusive and participatory processes may be more appropriate for navigating contested values, distributional impacts, and uncertainty in adaptation and resilience planning.

Overall, the panel illustrated that addressing systemic climate risks requires more than improved data or technical solutions alone. It calls for governance approaches that align science, finance, and political decision-making, recognise long-term and cross-sectoral interdependencies and support collective action across scales.

Figure 1: Participants of the 3rd I-DRRnF in Hamburg. Photo: Priscila Lazaro

6.2. Innovation Fair

As part of this year's I-DRRnF, the Innovation Fair invited all The HuT demonstrators to present a poster showcasing their activities, innovation and research in a dedicated session. To familiarise conference participants with the session, a short introduction was given in the plenary, and all attendees were invited to join a moderated walk from poster to poster. The aim of this session and the poster presentations was to foster exchange between the various demonstrators, other project partners and conference attendees.

The posters presented ten DRR case studies across Europe that test innovative approaches to managing and reducing climate-related risks. All demonstrators bring together scientists, technical experts, policymakers, practitioners, and local communities to co-develop and implement solutions. Since The HuT project brings together a diverse set of demonstrator arenas across Europe, each situated in regions where communities are confronted with different climate extremes and natural hazards. From heatwaves in Mediterranean cities to avalanches in Iceland and Switzerland, floods in Hungary to wildfires in Sardinia, the scope of the initiative is deliberately broad. The posters presented during the conference reflect this diversity, offering insights into how local contexts shape both the risks faced and the solutions pursued. The ten posters are summarised in the following section, and the original posters are attached in the Annex.

6.2.1. DEM 1, Valencia, Spain

DEM 1 presented a poster on heat and drought management in the coastal city of Valencia. In this demonstrator, climate risks are intensifying, particularly heatwaves, which have become longer, more severe, and increasingly lethal. Between May and August 2025 alone, 974 fatalities were attributed to high temperatures, during the third warmest summer on record at +1.6 °C above average. Historical analysis shows that heatwave events increased by two per decade between

1979 and 2014, with average durations extending from less than 10 days to about 25 days. Future projections suggest extreme temperatures can occur from April to November and a merging of heatwaves into fewer but longer events that are amplified by rising humidity.

To address these challenges, activities in the DEM focused on hazard reduction, exposure management, and vulnerability mitigation. Several approaches were showcased and discussed during the poster session. The WATER4CAST online platform, for example, enables seasonal drought forecasts at multiple timescales. Co-developed with users over a three-year period, the platform ensures accessibility and practical relevance for decision-making. To interpret temperature projections from a human-centred perspective, the platform team developed the Heat Index (HI), which captures the combined effects of temperature and humidity. In addition, a locally adapted version of the Safe Haven serious game (developed in The HuT project) was tested. This version included 13 strategies aimed at reducing hazard, exposure and vulnerability and 22 unique event cards to simulate realistic scenarios. Furthermore, barriers and enablers for the implementation of nature-based solutions, meant to reduce multiple and systemic risks in the city of Valencia, were analysed. Key barriers included limited technical and specialised knowledge, path dependency, specific regulations and limited funding; while enabling factors comprised political will, evidence of benefits, citizen participation and effective communication.

6.2.2. DEM 2, Val d’Aran Region, Spain

DEM 2 highlighted their work in the Val d’Aran, a headwater region of 620 km² in the Garona River basin, in the Spanish Pyrenees, which is prone to landslides, flash floods, debris flows, and river overflows. A significant flood–landslide event in June 2013 underscored the vulnerability of this mountainous area. The project emphasised the development of a Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MHEWS) capable of delivering timely, actionable alerts and enhancing resilience against increasingly frequent and severe climate extremes.

The initiative introduced a coupled hydrological–geotechnical modelling framework to capture multi-hazard processes and integrate them regionally for coordinated decision-making. Strategic densification of monitoring networks was achieved by through the installation of new sensors in previously unmonitored “blind spots.” Devices for measuring relative humidity, soil moisture, and temperature, and precipitation data were deployed and fed into a web-based IoT platform, which provides real-time and forecasted data, hazard maps, and a map-based view of hazard levels with a three-day forecast for floods and landslides. Automated alerts are disseminated via phone calls, SMS, email, and push notifications, while live access to the monitoring stations’ data supports operational decision-making. Awareness and preparedness activities, such as workshops, drills, and co-created public materials (infographics, safe-route maps, short videos), were complemented by partnerships with local high schools.

6.2.3. DEM 3, Lattari Mountains, Italy

DEM 3 presented a poster summarizing the different innovations under testing in the Lattari Mountains (including Sorrento and Amalfi Coasts) in Southern Italy, a region with many domestic and foreign tourists that faces increasing climate extremes. Key hazards include extreme precipitation triggering landslides in pyroclastic covers and where wildfires can act as predisposing factors, flash floods in small basins, convective events and hailstorms damaging crops and assets in the summer season. Additional cascading effects amongst these hazards show how systemic risks can manifest and spread. Current challenges include limited in situ monitoring coverage in complex terrain and the difficulties in translating technical data into actionable information.

The project showcased several innovative strategies designed to strengthen local disaster preparedness and risk literacy: (1) The release of a decision-support dashboard, co-developed

with the Municipality of Amalfi, which provides forecasts, monitoring data, and ready-to-use data into a one-stop-shop information hub; and (2) the use of Serious Gaming to raise community awareness, in particular among high school students, on landslide risk assessment and adaptation measures. Complementary activities include community-based monitoring via reports from hikers through a web app developed in KoboToolbox environment, IoT sensor networks to provide information about soil wetness recognized as a predisposing condition for geo-hydrological hazards, the design of prototype parametric insurance mechanisms to provide rapid compensation after events and climate proofing design of sewage systems by implementing a reversal impact chain approach.

6.2.4. DEM 4, Vilnius, Lithuania

The poster by DEM 4 presented the growing challenge of extreme rainfall and pluvial flooding in Vilnius. In the city, flooding events affect transport infrastructure, cultural heritage areas, and public spaces. Projections suggest more frequent and more intense rainfall events in the future. Hydraulic analyses of the historic centre revealed critical bottlenecks at major crossings and tunnels, and a limited drainage capacity in historic areas. The work in this demonstrator combined hydraulic modelling, precipitation data analysis, and participatory discussions with academics, policymakers, engineers, planners, cultural heritage specialists, and local communities. Different flooding scenarios were mapped to assess the return periods of certain impacts.

DEM 4 provided an overview of the results of the Vilnius DRR forum that had taken place in March 2025. Through interactive discussions, social tolerance of pluvial flooding of the capital city was tested, taking into account different precipitation scenarios. During this workshop, the importance of integrating climate adaptation actions and systemic approaches into urban planning was emphasised. Solutions identified during the local workshop included protecting and expanding green areas, enhancing meteorological data collection and monitoring, and promoting on-site rainwater storage and management. Technical measures such as installing accumulation tanks, enlarging permeable surfaces, and modernising the surface runoff system were complemented by social strategies, including education and awareness campaigns.

6.2.5. DEM 5, Hamburg/Glückstadt, Germany

The poster presented by DEM 5 featured activities in Glückstadt, Schleswig-Holstein. As a coastal city, Glückstadt faces increasing risks from climate extremes such as storms and flooding. The project presented its engagement in developing local climate stories and using narratives and storytelling to bring people together for action. The aims of the fieldwork include enhancing user-focused capacity building for early warning and long-term resilience, raising awareness among decision-makers and communities about expected weather-related risks, and engaging different sectors of society through innovative approaches that also consider systemic dynamics.

The project emphasised innovative community engagement, e.g. by collecting personal experiences from residents to develop a participatory Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) tool to support decision-making. It also developed an art-science collaboration with the local art association which brought together artists, schools also from the surrounding area, and residents to co-develop narratives around the elements of air, water, and earth. This collaboration culminated in the exhibition SAFE HAVEN, which was presented to the public for two months at the Palais für Aktuelle Kunst in Glückstadt. Moreover, dissemination efforts included newsletters, exhibitions, and public engagement activities that extended beyond Glückstadt into the wider region. The SAFE HAVEN exhibition was visited by The HuT consortium on the day preceding the I-DRRnF.

6.2.6. DEM 6, East Fjords, Iceland

DEM 6 presented a poster on their study site in Seyðisfjörður in Iceland's East Fjords. The community is highly exposed to gravitational hazards such as landslides and snow avalanches. In December 2020, intense rainfall triggered severe landslides that destroyed several houses and caused significant damage. Key needs of the community are to improve the monitoring and modelling of precipitation, enhance the dissemination of data and strengthen community involvement in risk identification.

The poster introduced two flagship activities: (1) workshops and focus group interviews with residents and volunteers, as well as with companies to identify community needs, and (2) the development of a dedicated website that responds to the identified needs and serves as a one-stop shop for all information on natural hazards. The website integrates real-time monitoring data from the Icelandic Meteorological Office, information from local police and road authorities for risk communication and provides educational material on avalanches and landslides, civil protection structures, hazard maps, defence measures, evacuation procedures, insurance, and trauma processing.

6.2.7. DEM 7, Tisza River Basin, Hungary

DEM7 presented a poster on their work in the Middle Tisza District in Hungary, a flatland region highly vulnerable to flooding. The area is part of the larger Danube River Basin (7,180 km² locally, with 56% endangered by floods), featuring more than 700 km of dike systems and over 4,300 km of channels. Key challenges include recurrent floods (that can result from both heavy rain events or long periods of lower intensity rain in combination with high runoff from snowmelt), droughts, inland excess water, and contamination risks. At the same time, municipalities often lack expertise and capacities for managing complex flood events.

To address these risks, the mobile application VIZ24 was developed and deployed. It provides dynamic real-time tools from a complex sensor network, including IoT technology, in combination with static data to support emergency response. Its features include interactive maps of channels, pump stations, reservoirs, settlement borders and flood risk zones, emergency and intervention plans, contact lists of responsible officials, an alarm system for heavy rain and a local risk assessment system for prolonged saturation and drought monitoring. Its risk assessments incorporate data such as soil types and topography, urban and rural flood protection measures, the condition of drainage systems, conditions of channels, and soil moisture. More than 300 users from municipalities, water management, and administrative authorities are registered.

6.2.8. DEM 8, Ogliastra, Italy

DEM 8 presented their work on wildfires in Ogliastra in Sardinia, Italy. The region is highly exposed to fires affecting forests and the wildland–urban interface (WUI). They are exacerbated by climate extremes and land abandonment. Key challenges include recurrent large wildfires driven by summer wind conditions, fuel accumulation from shrubland encroachment, and socio-economic vulnerabilities in rural communities. Historical climate data and future scenarios were analysed to project fire behaviour from 1991 to 2070. Projections suggest increasing fire size and intensity under climate change, reinforcing the need for adaptive land management and innovative instruments.

The demonstrator presented two flagship activities to address these risks: (1) The development of a modelling process that integrates science-based fire risk modelling with stakeholders' knowledge, policies, and governance for ensuring that the mitigating fire risk solutions developed are grounded in real-world needs, acceptable to stakeholders and feasible for implementation. This process included fire, vegetation, topography and climate data collection, climate scenario

analysis, landscape exposure assessments and land management scenarios that have been deliberated with stakeholders by conducting participatory mapping exercises and co-definition of adaptation strategies. (2) The development of a prototype of innovative insurance products to support communities and stakeholders in managing and mitigating wildfire impacts. This was based on an improved estimation of wildfire risks (through statistics of burned areas and fire intensity), exposure models, and modelling of forestry management options' effects on the vulnerability to wildfire damage. Forestry management options were shown to reduce vulnerability, enabling a 10% premium discount for exposures benefiting from ecological practices.

6.2.9. DEM 9, Dorset, United Kingdom

DEM 9 presented a poster focusing on their case study in Dorset, a county in Southwest England, which is a major tourist destination but faces significant vulnerabilities to climate-related hazards, including storms, coastal erosion, and cliff falls. The poster emphasised the importance of strong institutional partnerships, adaptive planning, and innovative public engagement formats. Key challenges addressed in the project include the complexity of integrating diverse hazard data, the need for consistent warning communication across different agencies and multiple hazards, and the difficulty of reaching diverse audiences such as tourists, landowners, councils, and emergency responders.

To address these, DEM9 assessed the warning value chain (Golding, 2022) for two storm events to evaluate successes, challenges, and lessons learned. Post-event analyses involved meteorologists, hydrometeorologists, civil contingency advisors, and scientists from multiple institutions. Group scoring exercises identified improvement themes such as optimising large data handling, strengthening warning evolution communication, and working toward unified risk and impact assessments. Solutions showcased include the installation of a new weather station in a high-tourism area prone to cliff falls, with data shared among local authorities, landowners, and universities, and new collaborations, leading to an MSc student prototype cliff hazard map donated for council use. Public engagement was expanded through articles in local tourism magazines and an art-science initiative, which encouraged audiences to interpret coastal risk through different lenses of responsibility and vulnerability.

6.2.10. DEM 10, Bern, Switzerland

DEM 10 presented a poster on protection forest (PF) management in Bern Canton, Switzerland. In this demonstrator, protection forests serve as critical nature-based solutions in safeguarding communities and infrastructure against natural hazards such as rockfalls, landslides, debris flows, snow avalanches, and floods, where often several of these hazards occur at the same time. Protection forests have been formally managed under national law for over 150 years. Today, they cover around 50% of Bern's forests and protect 60,000 inhabitants, 2,700 km of roads, and 127 km of railway tracks. While the long-standing forests are not directly an innovation, the application of NbS for DRR on a landscape level and some policy instruments (in particular the PROTECT praxis guidelines, which allow a harmonised and impartial assessment of biological and grey measures for DRR) can be considered innovative.

In the highlighted activity, the DEM10 team, together with other project partners, identified and analysed key enablers and barriers to protection forest management and implementation of the PROTECT Praxis guidelines, while also considering systemic risks. To this end, they conducted semi-structured interviews with experts from federal and cantonal authorities, academia, and risk management, alongside scientific and grey literature. Identified enablers include strong legal frameworks and guidelines, effective subsidies, and the multifunctionality of protection forests, which provide biodiversity and climate co-benefits. Despite their long-established role and

perceived importance, significant barriers existed as well: Barriers include concerns about PF resilience to climate change impacts, ungulate browsing limiting forest regeneration and workforce shortages. Limited expertise on forest dynamics, tensions between forestry and hazard management practitioners and the absence of non-gravitational hazards such as wildfires and floods in existing guidelines were also reported as factors hampering protection forest management. The poster presentation ended with recommendations to address these barriers and promote NBS upscaling.

6.3. Synthesis

Both the keynote and the demonstrators' presentations reflected on systemic risks. However, each contribution had a slightly different focus and highlighted different aspects, either through a conceptual lens, a sectoral lens or a specific case study. Together, they underscored the need to consider a systemic understanding of climate change impacts and interactions between people, ecosystems, infrastructure, and institutions for designing and implementing effective DRR solutions. Effective DRR, therefore, requires joint efforts and adaptable innovations in science, technology, and governance.

The keynote presentations showcased a large variety of systemic risk dimensions, ranging from conceptual considerations to sectoral examples. They spanned across systems governance, digitalisation and artificial intelligence, improved assessment frameworks, response mechanisms, systemic risks connected to current developments around the UN science-policy landscape, systemic risks in specific sectors such as finance, food systems, or urbanisation, understanding future vulnerabilities, and questions of justice. Thereby, they familiarised the audience and The HuT demonstrators with current academic debates and perspectives. They stimulated vivid discussions that reflected the questions that the demonstrators face when implementing DRR solutions.

The demonstrators' presentations showed how DRR challenges are tackled in practice and what considerations emerge in the implementation of risk mitigation measures. The posters reflected the demonstrators' joint ambition to explore how scientific innovation, technological tools, and participatory governance can strengthen DRR. Across the demonstrators, certain themes recurred. Climate extremes are intensifying universally, whether through prolonged heatwaves, heavier rainfall, more frequent storms, or greater wildfire risks. Throughout Europe, this growing exposure has intensified the need for adaptive planning and for systems that can translate complex scientific and technical data into clear, actionable information and strategies for decision-makers and the wider public. Demonstrators highlighted current challenges, including gaps in monitoring coverage, limited workforce capacity, and communicating systemic risks. Yet, they showcased a wealth of innovations across various levels, from technical innovations to governance mechanisms to innovations in social and community engagement, such as citizen science programs, educational games, or art-science collaborations. The differences between demonstrators underscore the importance of context, such as cultural, regional and geographical factors in shaping DRR strategies. For example, urban areas prioritised infrastructure and communication, while rural and mountain regions focused more on sensor networks, as well as ecological and landscape-based approaches.

Across the keynote and demonstrators' presentations, the need for a systemic understanding of hazards and risks reappeared and, likewise, the shared understanding that governance systems need to be adaptive and inclusive to effectively address systemic risks while adequately considering vulnerability in DRR. Also, the opportunities and concerns associated with new digital technologies recurred across keynotes and demonstrators. These included the potential of digitalisation for governance and AI applications for forecasting and assessing systemic risks, as

well as IoT applications that are piloted in several demonstrators. Importantly, the presentations highlighted the need for normative frameworks to guide systemic risk governance, an issue that could be further explored by the demonstrators. Other links could be drawn between the insightful presentations on the systemic dependencies within financial systems and the development of insurance products in certain demonstrators. Finally, the presentation on Climate Change and Existential Risk called for mobilising the public to tackle climate risks – an approach that is taken up through stakeholder engagement work and educational activities undertaken in many demonstrators.

7. Conclusions

This report summarises the results of the third I-DRRnF, which took place on 24 September 2025 in Hamburg, Germany. The forum focused on systemic risks in the context of multi-hazard disaster risk reduction (DRR) and explored how scientific innovation, technological tools, and participatory governance can be combined to strengthen resilience. Presentations and discussions covered conceptual, sectoral and practical perspectives, reflecting the complexity of systemic risk approaches and multi-hazard management.

The special strength of this year's I-DRRnF lied in the large number and diversity of participants, which included researchers and practitioners from different institutions across Europe, including but going well beyond The HuT project partners. The wealth of presentations, discussions and exchanges contributed to cross-learning, sharing of recent research and DRR innovations that cross-fertilise each other. The demonstrators and posters presented at the forum collectively highlight the multidimensional nature of disaster risk reduction (DRR) and the systemic risks that increasingly shape our societies, to which DRR efforts need to respond. Despite these variations, a common learning is that effective DRR requires collaboration across sectors, disciplines, integration of local knowledge, and governance structures capable of learning and adapting as risks evolve.

Overall, the forum addressed a wide range of current challenges related to systemic and climate risks, which provided inspiration for both science and practice. It supported the ongoing efforts within The HuT to develop DRR strategies that better account for systemic risks. The discussions confirmed that systemic risk is not an abstract or theoretical concern in DRR, but a practical challenge that directly shapes the effectiveness of DRR efforts in a context of accelerating climate extremes. Throughout the forum, participants emphasised that risks emerge not only from hazards themselves, but from how societies are prepared and how they govern, finance, communicate, and respond to them. This reinforces the need for DRR approaches that explicitly acknowledge interdependencies, feedbacks, and uneven distributions of vulnerability.

For The HuT project, the forum provided both validation of the work done to date and direction for future activities. The demonstrators' experiences show that working across multiple hazards already entails engagement with systemic dimensions, even when not explicitly framed as such. At the same time, the discussions pointed to areas where systemic perspectives could be further strengthened, including the modelling of vulnerability and exposure dynamics, cross-sectoral coordination, the role of finance and insurance, and the use of normative frameworks to guide decision-making in case studies. In conclusion, the I-DRRnF in Hamburg demonstrated that integrating systemic risk thinking into DRR is crucial to account for intensifying climate impacts and their intersections with social, economic, and political dynamics.

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Annex

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes

DEM 1 - Valencia, (Spain)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/valencia/>

VALENCIA, A MEDITERRANEAN COASTAL CITY EXPOSED TO EXTREME HEAT AND DROUGHTS

August 2025, 3rd warmest summer.+1.6°C above average

4 consecutive very warm Augusts (2022-2025)

974 fatalities attributable to high temperatures in the Valencia Region between May 15 and August 31, 2025

Fatalities attributable to high temperature

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

We integrated the Heat Index (HI) to capture the combined effect of temperature and humidity, providing a human-centered perspective on heatwave impacts.

SAFE HAVEN: HEATWAVES, THE (SERIOUS) GAME

- Choose between 13 adaptation strategies to reduce hazard, exposure, and vulnerability
- 22 unique cards of events
- Internally tested and iterated to improve the educational experience

BARRIERS AND ENABLERS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NBS

BARRIERS: Lack of technical and specialized knowledge, Dependence on conventional practices, Regulatory guidelines and specific regulations, Limited funding.

ENABLERS: Political will and long-term commitment, Generation of evidence, Citizen participation, Communication strategies.

DROUGHT SEASONAL AND FORECAST

Seasonal Forecast SPI 6 from ECMWF_SEASS at (39.5°, -0.5°)

Month	Dry period (%)	Normal WPF (%)	Wet period (%)
September	25.49	72.55	1.96
October	13.73	82.35	3.92
November	19.61	68.63	11.76
December	3.92	78.43	17.65
January	11.79	72.55	15.69
February	9.80	66.67	23.53
March	27.45	64.90	17.6

Legend: Dry period (≥ 75%, ≥ 50%, < 50%), Normal period (≥ 75%, ≥ 50%, < 50%), Wet period (≥ 75%, ≥ 50%, < 50%), No indicator.

Prolonged drought trends (GPDI) in the Bajo Turia, Valencia

- Online platform (WATER4CAST) allows sharing predictions for drought and other relevant water-related variables.
- New implementation of drought indices SPI and SPEI at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months.
- Drought analysis also performed at the long-term taking climate change projections.
- Climate change projections to be added into the platform soon.
- Online platform co-designed with users during the last 3 years.
- Access:

CLIMATE CHANGE FUTURE HEATWAVES PROJECTIONS

Longer and more severe events

- Historical Trends (1979–2014): Heatwave events increased by two per decade, with average duration extending from less than 10 days to about 25 days.
- Future Projections (2075–2100): Predicted extreme temperatures from April to November, with springs exceeding 35 °C, prolonged autumns, and a potential need to revise heatwave definitions and seasonal boundaries.
- Shift in Heatwave Patterns: Forecasted a decrease in event frequency by ~2.7 per decade by 2075–2100, and as heatwaves merge into fewer but longer events.
- Amplified Risk from Humidity: Noted that rising humidity alongside temperature increases health risks, emphasizing the need for urgent resilience strategies in Valencia and similar Mediterranean cities.

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1 Motivation

Communities face multiple hazards—landslides, flash floods, debris flows, river overflows—often triggered by the same extreme events.
Prediction is not enough: what's needed is a **Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MH-EWS)** that delivers timely, actionable alerts.

Our aim

- Couple a hydrological-geotechnical model to capture multi-hazard processes.
- Regional integration for real-time, coordinated decisions.
- Install new sensors in under-monitored areas (rain and soil moisture).
- Web platform for real-time data, forecasted data and hazard maps.
- Operational MH-EWS, co-designed with UPC, ARANTEC and local stakeholders for usability and adoption.

4 IoT Monitoring

- Strategic densification covers previously unmonitored "blind spots".
- LoRa-based telemetry soil-moisture and AWS data in real time with QA/QC.
- Continuous observations validate and calibrate the coupled hydro-geotechnical model and its forecasts.

Figure 4. Installed monitoring station (Type 2)

5 IoT Platform

- Map-based view of hazard levels by zone with a 3-day forecast for floods and landslides.
- Automated alerting via phone calls, SMS, email and push notifications from configurable thresholds.
- Live access to the station network and other key layers (radar/snow, exposure, safe routes) for operations.

Figure 5. Landing page of HuT Dem2 IoT Platform.

6 Awareness & Preparedness

- Partnership with the local high school for student research projects using DEM2 data and tools.
- Workshops, light drills, and co-creation of public materials (infographics, safe-route maps, short videos).

DEM 2 Team:

- UPC: <https://deca.upc.edu/es>
- ARANTEC: <https://www.arantec.com>

Stakeholders:

- Consellh Generau d'Aran
- Pompiers d'Aran
- Institut d'Aran
- Lauègi d'Aran
- Office national des forêts (ONF)
- CC Pyrénées Haut Garonnaises

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes

DEM 3 "Lattari Mountains" (Italy)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/lattari-mountains/>

The context

Southern Italy: 300 km², 32 municipalities, about 450K inhabitants

Main hazards tackled

- Landslides** in pyroclastic soil involving, in some cases, the terraced landscape.
- Flash floods** affecting very small, orographically complex basins (mainly in Autumn)
- Fires**, also acting as predisposing factors for slope instability (Summer touristic season)
- Severe storms (e.g., hails)** affecting crops and assets, also occurring outside the wet season

Environmental and cultural heritage, e.g., Amalfi Coast (UNESCO World Heritage)

Millions of domestic and foreign tourists hosted each year

Main innovations developed

- Dashboard:** to support local administrators in managing weather-induced emergencies by providing monitoring data, asset and vulnerability mapping, and meteorological forecasts.
- Community monitoring:** developed in the KoboToolbox environment for collecting reports from hikers and trekkers on potential hazards that are difficult to monitor in mountain areas.
- IoT monitoring:** installation of low-cost sensors in areas insufficiently covered, or for variables not currently monitored, that regulate the occurrence of climate/weather-driven phenomena.
- Serious Gaming:** to raise community awareness (targeting high school students) on landslide risk assessment and the identification of adaptation measures. It is complemented by educational material for in-class lessons.
- Innovative insurance mechanisms:** prototype parametric insurance products (with payouts not subject to expert verification) designed to provide an initial compensation that covers immediate expenses in the aftermath of an event.
- Climate proofing planning:** application of a reversal impact chain approach (from impacts back to drivers) to the design of infrastructure, accounting for the potential effects of climate change.

The Dashboard

What	Why	How
<p>The Dashboard is designed as a one-stop-shop for information management. It does not generate new data but rather optimizes access to existing information, particularly during the critical phases preceding or immediately following a potential geo-hydrological event.</p>	<p>The Dashboard addresses a set of critical issues that emerged during the co-design and development:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding of forecast information Understanding of monitoring data Improving monitoring Capitalizing on existing knowledge Exploiting local knowledge 	<p>The entire structure of the Dashboard has been co-developed with local decision-makers, in particular with the Municipality of Amalfi. The technological development was led by one of the project partners, ARANTEC, which capitalized on the experience gained in other decision-support tools. This also enabled the parallel development of similar solutions in other contexts (e.g., DEM2 in Val d'Aran). The Dashboard capitalizes also the efforts in other innovations developed in The HuT (e.g., IoT)</p>

Safe Haven – Landslides

What	Why	How
<p>Games may be powerful tools to increase risk awareness. "Safe Haven – Landslides" is a board game designed to be played with high school students (and playful adults) to address, by means of playing, issues related to landslides, to the risk they pose and to the many important factors that need to be considered to manage landslide risk.</p>	<p>"Safe Haven – Landslides" also serves a broader purpose by supporting the improvement of disaster risk literacy, defined as "the ability of an individual to access, read, understand, and use the information necessary to make informed decisions and follow instructions in the context of mitigation, preparation, response, and recovery during a disaster."</p>	<p>"Safe Haven – Landslides" has undergone an extended testing phase with a variety of audiences (FuturoRemoto, EGU 2024 and 2025) to assess several key aspects of the game:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ scientific robustness; ✓ playability, i.e., how enjoyable and engaging the gameplay experience truly was; ✓ role of game master (if not playing with pre-set scenarios), in guiding and regulating game dynamics.

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes
DEM 4 "Vilnius" (Lithuania)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/vilnius/>

Vilnius DRR forum

Extreme rainstorms and urban pluvial flooding - measures adapting to climate change

2025 03 12 Vilnius municipality on the framework of Vilnius - Green capital of Europe 2025; moderator dr. G. Godienė

Academics, policy makers, engineers practitioners, urban and landscape planners, specialists of cultural heritage, youth and local communities

Presentation session

- The goals and activities of the "The HuT" project
- The lessons of the extreme rainfall in Valencia, Spain, 2024
- Vilnius Climate adaptation actions
- Vilnius streets flooding cases in 2013–2024 reported by public media. Official data on precipitation.
- The hydraulic analysis of the impact of precipitation on the drainage system in the pilot area of the Vilnius Historic Center.

Some Vilnius streets flooding cases in 2013–2024 reported by media
V. Medvytis, LANS,
G. Stankunavicius, G. Godienė, VU

Hydraulic analysis of the impact of precipitation on the drainage system in the Vilnius historic center pilot area.
Krišnaus Viršilaus, CMCC

Inclusive Discussion session

What solutions/measures of DRR are possible and acceptable? The list of DRR on pluvial flooding measures and their evaluation prioritising due criteria of effectiveness, financial loss reduction, equity, and affordability

Social tolerance to heavy rains and the resulting flooding of Vilnius streets, as well as other consequences of heavy rains

5 mixed groups; 8 categories of urban streets and other urban elements

5* scenarios of inundations (depth vs persistence)

5** categories of tolerance according return period

- 1 scenario: Impassable, flooding >25 cm, >24 hrs. Landslides, major pavement damage, fallen trees, power outages, >12 hrs.
- 2 scenario: Impassable, flooding >20 cm, 8-24 hrs. Major pavement damage, fallen trees, power outages, >12 hrs.
- 3 scenario: Flooding 10-25 cm 3-8 hrs. Fallen trees, power outages, 3-12 hrs.
- 4 scenario: Flooding 10-25 cm <3 hrs. Fallen trees, power outages, <3 hrs.
- 5 scenario: Flooding 5-10 cm 6-12 hrs.

Urban element	Possible consequences of rainstorms: I would feel as if it happened...				
	1 scenario	2 scenario	3 scenario	4 scenario	5 scenario
A Fast traffic streets and highways	0	0,6	0,8	1,2	2,1
B Main streets	0	0,6	0,8	2,2	2,8
C Main streets	0,4	0,8	1,2	2,4	2,8
D Side/secondary streets	0,5	1,2	2	2,8	3,4
Yards	0,5	1	1,8	2,2	3,2
Historic center and other cultural heritage areas	0	0,2	0,1	0,6	1,2
Public spaces, squares	1,8	1,8	2,8	3	3,8
Other important public spaces	0	0,2	0,8	1,2	2,2
Average score	0,125	0,8	1,325	1,95	2,7

- Protection of natural areas, surfaces and Greening initiatives
- Meteorological data collection and monitoring
- Storage and management rain water on-site, less disposal
- Installation of water storage/accumulation tanks
- Education and awareness
- Enlargement of permeable surfaces
- Modernization of the surface runoff system of Vilnius

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes

DEM 5 "Schleswig-Holstein State" (Germany)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/schleswig-holstein-state/>

The following 3 Climate Events are considered in Demonstrator 5

Art-science collaboration within the narrative process

To find "their narrative" together with Glückstadt residents, we initiated the SAFE HAVEN exhibition with the Palace for Contemporary Art in Glückstadt and its integrated local art association.

We gave the Exhibition Board input on The HuT and, in particular, on our guidelines "The HuT for Me and You" created for the development of narratives. The curators selected three artists who have worked on the different elements of air, water, and earth. In addition, the exhibition concept was taken up in the art classes of different schools in and around Glückstadt.

The overall result is currently on show in the SAFE HAVEN exhibition. The opening was very well attended by almost 80 participants of various ages.

The art-science format has proven to be a strong promoter and multiplier for our project.

Our long-term goal is to provide an infrastructure for a future Climate Advisory Council in Glückstadt through the exhibition's side program.

Interactions with the audience

→ Collection of personal experiences with extreme weather events and reactions

→ Post-its with recommendations and wishes for a Glückstadt that is better prepared to deal with extreme weather events

→ We got 94 Post-its with recommended actions

Public engagement through the exhibition

The exhibition includes a Communication space where visitors are invited to share their thoughts on The HuT's narrative and offer their personal contributions to a resilient future.

Expanding DEM5 activities into the surrounding region via the exhibition process

Development of a participatory Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) as a decision support tool

	Relative weight (p.16)	Relative weight (p.17)	Relative weight (p.18)	Relative weight (p.19)	Relative weight (p.20)
Adaptation	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Resilience	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Costs	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Land use	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Ecology	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Health	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Quality of life	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Security	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Social justice	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Transparency	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Trust	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Well-being	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Work-life balance	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25

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Introduction

Mass movements are common in Iceland, including snow avalanches and landslides. Landslides have caused fatalities and extensive damage in many areas of the country. After a period of intense rainfall in the Eastfjords in December 2020, the town of Seyðisfjörður experienced severe landslides. Several houses were destroyed, causing financial and emotional damage to the inhabitants. Thankfully, there was no loss of life. Catastrophic snow avalanches are also known in Seyðisfjörður, the most severe one caused 24 fatalities in 1885.

Figure 1. A destructive landslide fell in Seyðisfjörður on December 18, 2020. Photo taken by the local police.

The main needs of DEM 6 in the HuT project have been identified as follows:

- To improve the monitoring and modelling of rainfall patterns that trigger landslides and snow avalanches.
- To improve dissemination of data and information to inhabitants.
- To permit a higher involvement of communities in risk identification.

The Icelandic partners in The HuT project are the Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO), the Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management (DCPEM) and the research centre Austurbú representing the municipalities in the East fjords.

Two flagship activities are described here 1) Visit to Seyðisfjörður, which involved focus group interviews and visits to five key companies in the area. 2) Creating and building a website that will serve as a communication and educational portal between the authorities and residents.

Flagship activity 1: Workshops in Seyðisfjörður

In January 2023, the partners in DEM 6 visited Seyðisfjörður. Part of the group took part in focus group interviews, and the other part visited key companies.

Five key companies in Seyðisfjörður were visited: The Museum of Technology, Sildarvinnslan fisheries operator, LungA school, Studio Ströndin, and Herðubreið community centre.

Two focus groups were put together to reflect the views of the general population and the views of volunteers who participated in work during and following the landslides in 2020. The first group included residents in risk areas, and the second group consisted of volunteers.

Question 1

The goal of the project is to launch a website that will be hosted by the DCPEM and provides information and education. For the website to be as useful as possible, it is very valuable to get feedback from the inhabitants on what is important to have on such a site.

What do you think is important to present on the website in terms of real-time information and other information?

Question 2

If we look at the practical aspects of the website, for example, what is the best way to find the website? Is it through the DCPEM website, the municipality or the IMO?

Which languages are necessary for the information on the website to be of the best use?

How is information best communicated on the site if a natural hazard situation arises or new information comes in? In general, how is it best to communicate information to residents living in a natural hazard area?

Is there anything else you can think of regarding practical issues with the website and sharing information from it?

Question 3

We can learn from the landslides of 2020 to build better information sharing and education for residents of natural hazard areas. If we look ahead with the knowledge we have gained in the past years and try to think about how we can use the experience from 2020:

What went well and what could have been done better? Was there something missing or was something exaggerated?

Figure 2. A meeting with residents in Seyðisfjörður in January 2023.

Focus group results

The focus groups identified the following topics that the participants consider to be important when it comes to information provision before, during and after a natural adverse event.

- **Education:**
 - General education about nature literacy
 - Educational videos based on local matters
- **Announcements:**
 - General education about nature literacy
 - Educational videos based on local matters
- **Monitoring devices:**
 - Accessible and understandable information on the monitoring devices in place
 - Data from monitoring devices
- **Announcements:**
 - Ways for residents to submit tips and photos
 - Information on hazard areas and real estates
 - Various ways of submitting notifications to the residents
- **Emergency:**
 - Information on contingency plans
 - Reaction exercises
- **Follow-up procedures:**
 - Information on post processing
 - Education on insurance coverage
 - Education on trauma processing

Figure 3. Example of data from one of three Shappo Arviss located in townships in Seyðisfjörður for monitoring deep seabed movements.

Flagship activity 2: Development of a website

A website is under development that will serve as a one-stop shop for all information on natural hazards as well as other hazards the community in Seyðisfjörður faces. The construction of the website is based on results from the focus groups.

Figure 4. One-stop shop website design that will be hosted by the Department of Civil Protection.

The main information on the website can be classified as following:

- Educational material on different aspects related to snow avalanches and landslides such as history, monitoring, hazard maps and defence structures
- Educational material on the civil protection structure such as insurances, evacuation procedures, trauma processing etc.
- Avalanche and landslide forecasts as well as data from monitoring instruments
- Announcements during periods of increased hazard
- Announcements during low-risk periods

The website will be hosted by the Department of Civil Protection (DCPEM). It will gather data and information from various sources, such as from the Icelandic Met Office, the local police and the road authorities. As a part of the HuT project the Seyðisfjörður website will be tested by the focus groups of residents, business owners and response parties who will give feedback. The website will serve as a prototype for similar websites for other municipalities that face various types of hazard and become a part of the website system of DCPEM.

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes

DEM 7 "Tisza River Basin" (Hungary)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/tisza-river-basin/>

Danube River Basin

Length: 2860 km
Countries: 10
River basin countries: 19

River basin
817000 km²

Middle Tisza District Water Directorate

Area: 2140 km²
58% endangered by flood
207.8 km dike system
621.7 km dikeless

Conditions of Middle Tisza district:

- Flat land areas
- Main rivers: Tisza, Zagyva
- Lake Tisza – Kisköre barrage
- Main rural use: arable land
- 105 settlements

Main water management related challenges on the Tisza River Basin:

- Flood (fluvial and pluvial)
- Drought
- Inland excess water
- Water contamination

VIZ24 mobil application

The protection against pluvial flood in urban areas is responsible the affected municipality. In general the municipalities do not have the right professional staff. In case of emergency situation the Middle Tisza District Water Directorate made the VIZ24 mobile application in order to help the activities of municipalities at their water defense.

The main functions of VIZ24:

- Maps (Channels, Pump stations, Rain reservoirs, Borders of settlements, Pluvial flood risk map, Defense level of pluvial flood)
- Contains emergency plans, intervention plans
- Contains phone numbers of responsible people
- Alarm system in case of heavy rain
- Risk assessment

Users can download the application from Google Play or App Store but only the water directorate can give access.

There are 3 level of user:

- Municipalities
- Water management experts
- Administration

The VIZ24 mobil application has more than 300 registered users.

Risk assessment

Vulnerability factors:

1. Area at risk of pluvial flooding (type of soil, geographical situation) *Static data*
2. Municipal pluvial flood protection levels (urban) *Dynamic data*
3. Water directorate's (KÖTIVIZIG) pluvial flood protection levels (rural) *Dynamic data*
4. Condition of drainage systems in settlements (urban area) *Static data*
5. Condition of receivers (bigger channels) *Static data*
6. Soil moisture status (Decagon 5TM on 6 different depth) *Dynamic data IoT*

Multipurposes uses of draught monitoring gauges

**Soil moisture sensor
Decagon 5TM – GSM**

FLAGSHIP 1: Development of a **Modeling process** that integrates, at local level, science-based fire risk modeling with stakeholders knowledge, policies and governance for ensuring that the mitigating fire risk solutions developed are grounded in real-world needs, acceptable to stakeholders, and feasible for implementation.

FLAGSHIP 2: Development of a **Prototype of Innovative Insurance Products** to support communities and stakeholders in managing and mitigating wildfire impacts.

The use of DEM8 analyses enabled the development of a prototype forest fire insurance product tailored to the Sardinia region, named **"Fire Safe Community"**. The product's pricing was established using a bespoke natural catastrophe model.

Statistics on wildfires, mean burned area and wildfire intensity, provided by the demonstrator, have been used to design and calibrate the nat cat model used to estimate the risk covered by the product.

A synthetic portfolio, based on urban density and exposure amounts representative of a likely exposure distribution, has been produced to estimate risk related to concentration of events and obtain finite insurance premiums.

Forestry management operations influence the vulnerability to wildfire damage and, consequently the underlying risk used to calculate insurance premiums. Modeling these effects resulted in a 10% reduction in the premium. This reduction was adopted as the discount to be applied to exposures benefiting from ecological forestry management practices. Such mechanism enables the financing of risk reduction actions by communities and, therefore, enabling Community-Based Catastrophe Insurance (CBCI) underwriting schemes.

The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes

DEM 9 "Dorset" (United Kingdom)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/dorset/>

DEM9 (Dorset, UK)

Dorset is a county in Southwest England on the English Channel coast. The Jurassic coast is included as a UNESCO World Heritage site. It represents a key tourist destination with multiple areas exhibiting vulnerability to climate-related hazards. In this poster, we highlight three recent activities undertaken by the Met Office (MO) and British Geological Survey (BGS) as part of DEM9 involving research into **communications to support decision making**.

Warning value chain assessments for DEM9

DEM9 assessed the full warning value chain for Storm Eunice (18 Feb 2022) and Storm Ciarán (2 Nov 2023), focusing on southern England. Eunice had widespread wind hazards, while Ciarán, though smaller in area, was a multi-hazard event.

Neal et al. (2025) evaluated the successes, challenges, and lessons from these warnings using the warning value chain framework—a model of interconnected expertise and information flow. A **WMO HIWeather** questionnaire guided a detailed assessment of the information and decisions across the value chain for these two storms.

Post-event analysis included input from meteorologists, hydrometeorologists, civil contingency advisors, and scientists from the **Met Office, Flood Forecasting Centre, and British Geological Survey**. A group scoring exercise for each storm and value chain component identified **three key improvement themes**.

Streamlining information flow

- Optimising the handling of large volumes data
- Summary tools / multi-model / multi-ensemble / blended / seamless
- Co-development of tools across value chain components and hazards

Improving warning communication

- Maximise use of the impact matrix
- Strengthen warning evolution communication
- Enhance the effectiveness of multi-hazard warning communication
- Build on the success of storm naming

Enhancing cross-organisational collaboration

- Deeper collaboration between NHP partners to improve hazard assessments
- Enhance consistency in how warnings are displayed for various hazards
- Work towards a unified risk and impact assessment

Neal, R., Robbins, J., Tittle, H., Keates, S., Cox, D., Fenwick, K., Goodman, A., Evans, D., Freeborough, K., Dashwood, C., Gammon, E. (2025) Warning Value Chain Assessments for Storms Eunice (2022) and Ciarán (2023): Insights and Recommendations. Submitted to *Weather and Forecasting* on 25 April 2025.

Organisations involved in the UK Natural Hazards Partnership

Improved cross-organisational working

Effective **multi-hazard early warning systems** rely on strong **cross-organisational collaboration** to deliver timely, actionable insights to enhance national resilience. A shared goal unites partners: to anticipate, communicate, and mitigate hazard impacts through coordinated science, data integration, and operational delivery. Success is defined by **improved readiness and response**.

Recognising diverse expertise is essential. The **UK Natural Hazard Partnership** unites experts to enhance hazard readiness through science and coordination, delivering research and advice. Integrating complex data enables informed decisions on hazard timing, location, causes, and impacts although requires cross-organisational working.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), clear roles, and data-sharing boost efficient hazard response. Embedded reviews and adaptive planning drive continuous improvement. Working together we are building on these practices to build a resilient UK hazard science community, enabling timely, coordinated, and evidence-based decisions for natural hazard events.

Strengthening resilience through engagement

In DEM 9, stakeholder engagement continues to emphasise the need for **sustained collaboration** and **coherent communication** around weather, natural hazards, and climate-related risks. A knowledge-exchange workshop with the Local Resilience Forum (June 2023) explored how hazard and impact information is received by user groups and supports decision-making, strengthening partnerships and sparking new collaborations.

A key development is the installation of a weather station at West Bay, a high-tourism area prone to cliff falls. Data is now shared with local authorities, landowners, the Met Office, and Leeds University, where an MSc student produced a prototype cliff hazard map for council use.

Our partnership with Dorset Coast Forum—a multi-sectoral organisation advancing sustainable coastal development—has been instrumental. Engagement at their Annual Meeting (October 2024) revealed regional communication challenges and priorities. In summer 2025, published a public engagement article in *Resort Dorset* magazine (100,000 copies), extending hazard messaging into tourist hotspots.

The article builds on our art-science initiative from the British Geological Survey Open Day (June 2024), using a hand-painted image titled "What do you see?" to prompt reflection on coastal risk. It encouraged diverse audiences—tourists, landowners, councils, lifeguards—to interpret the same beach scene through different lenses of responsibility and vulnerability.

By reframing summer safety messaging to include cliff hazards, the article supports inclusive risk communication and will feature at Sidmouth Science Festival (October 2025) to further explore public perceptions of coastal risk.

- Resort Dorset Magazine Spring issue: <https://www.resortdorset.com/read/>
- Resort Dorset online article: <https://www.resortdorset.com/features/227/Coastal+Safety+-+Remember+the+Cliffs!/>
- What do you see? Scan the QR code or go to <https://www.bgs.ac.uk/discovering-geology/earth-hazards/landslides/cliffs/safety-remember-the-cliffs/> for the answers.

New weather station at West Bay and "what do you see?" art-initiative to support risk perception understanding and communication BGS © UKRI 2025

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The Human-Tech Nexus: Building a safe haven to cope with climate extremes
DEM 10 "Bern Canton" (Switzerland)
<https://thehut-nexus.eu/territory/berne-canton/>

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Upscaling nature-based solutions (NbS): Protection forest enablers and barriers

Introduction

- Protection forests (PF)**
- Protect against rockfalls, landslides, debris flows, snow avalanches and floods
 - Are traditionally used in Switzerland and formally managed under national law for 150 years
 - 50% (95,700 ha) of all forests in Bern have a protective function
 - They protect 60,000 inhabitants, 2,700 km of roads and 127 km of train tracks
 - NaiS ("Sustainability in protection forests") guidelines provide clear management advice to practitioners
- PROTECTpraxis guidelines**
- Guidelines to assess efficiency and return of investment of measures against natural hazards; fully implemented in 2025
 - Harmonize assessment of biological measures and grey measures; biological measures include PF and other NbS
 - Directly impact hazard maps

Research design

Research questions:

1. What are the key governance enablers and barriers of NbS/biological measures for DRR, in Bern (and beyond)?
2. What role do the recent biological measure guidelines (PROTECTpraxis) play?

Literature review on protection forest and NbS policy in Bern and Switzerland

Semi-structured interviews with key experts on PF and other NbS (N=14); interviewees included representatives from cantons, federal office for the environment, risk management, research & academia

Content analysis using Nvivo

Results

Conclusions & policy recommendations for NbS upscaling

<p>Strengthen the biodiversity and climate nexus</p> <p>Recognize biodiversity-climate interactions in policy frameworks: E.g. adaptive silviculture practices (mixed-species, assisted migration) as well as biodiversity-enhancing practices (using deadwood, managing invasive species). Incentivize these practices through subsidies.</p> <p>Establish a joint risk task force to develop planning responses that consider biodiversity-climate linkages, synergies and feedbacks.</p>	<p>Mitigate ungulate browsing pressure</p> <p>Mandate regional game management plans that include ecological targets and adapted hunting quotas.</p> <p>Subsidize protective measures, such as fencing in vulnerable areas, especially where afforestation is critical for slope stability.</p> <p>Introduce forest regeneration monitoring to track recovery success and target problem areas.</p>	<p>Address workforce gaps in PF and multi-risk management</p> <p>Add interdisciplinary modules to forestry and natural hazard curricula and training programs.</p> <p>Mandate interdisciplinary consultations in PROTECTpraxis application, e.g. by requiring involvement of at least one expert outside the applicant's core discipline.</p> <p>Include non-gravitational hazards (wildfires, floods) in NaiS modules.</p>	<p>Strengthen uptake and implementation of PROTECTpraxis</p> <p>Mandate PROTECTpraxis in all funded risk reduction planning.</p> <p>Provide financial incentives for early adoption, such as one-time subsidies to consultancies adopting the new methodology or including it in tenders.</p> <p>Organize cross-sectoral training workshops for engineers, ecologists, foresters, and hazard management practitioners.</p>	<p>Enhance multi-risk and cascading risk integration</p> <p>Create multi-risk focal points to coordinate between different units.</p> <p>Pilot multi-hazard risk planning, e.g. on test sites for multi-risks.</p> <p>Launch a training and terminology harmonization initiative to create a common understanding of multi-risk. E.g. co-developing tools for identifying hazard-interaction types or combining NbS, grey, and organizational measures.</p>
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Poster based on:
- Aguilera Rodriguez J., Martin J.G.C., Linerooth-Bayer J., Menin A., Fernandez-Ortega A.G., Huland E., Becali V., Rubia A., Scolobig A., Stoffel M., Stoffel M. (2025), D5.13 "Innovative policy/governance enablers for multi-risk DRR". The HuT. <https://zenodo.org/records/13543888>

Further publications developed within DEM10:
- Aachenberger J., Scolobig A., Huang Luchmann J., Calvello M., Stoffel M. (2025), "Barriers and enablers to stakeholder engagement in the co-creation of disaster risk reduction solutions", *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2025.105391>
- Martin J.G.C., Scolobig A., Linerooth-Bayer J., Imhard J., Aguilera Rodriguez J., Fresolone-Caporaso A., Oen A. "The nature-based solution implementation gap: a review of nature-based solution governance barriers and enablers", *Journal of Environmental Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126007>
- Bhondari C., Scolobig A., Abderhalden J., Weyrich P., Stoffel M. (2025) "Risk communication policies and strategies in Nepal and Switzerland: a comparative study", *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2025.105773>
Submitted:
- Aguilera Rodriguez J.J., Scolobig A., Martin J.G.C., Linerooth-Bayer J. "Implementing nature-based solutions: insights from private contractors and consultants" in review in *Nature-Based Solutions*
In preparation (titles are preliminary/work in progress):
- Huland E. et al. "Spilling barriers to multi-hazard disaster risk reduction: Lessons from early warning systems and nature-based solutions"
- Rohrer M. et al. "Spilling barriers to multi-hazard disaster risk reduction: Lessons from early warning systems and nature-based solutions"
- Rohrer M. et al. "High-intensity precipitation events and their spatial and temporal interpolation in the catchment scale by remote-sensing and model-based tools like INGA and 'CombiPrecip'"

